

An SDN-enabled Path Computation Element for Autonomous Multi-Band Optical Transport Networks

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Abstract

This paper reports on the design, implementation, and validation of an SDN control plane for Multi-Band Optical Networks with externalized Path Computation. The SDN control plane relies on extending current open and standard interfaces to support dynamic service management and decoupled path computation services on Multi-Band optical networks while accounting for physical layer impairments, which is critical for successful service provisioning. We detail the Multi-band Optical Network Resource management and optimization engine for transparent and translucent networks. The system is experimentally validated in a 22-ROADM BT network with emulated hardware showing the performance of the control plane and the considered workflows.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Networked Intelligence, a term that designates the convergence of Information, Communication and Operation Technologies, is the driver behind the revolutionary changes Industry 4.0 evangelizes [1]. As part of Networked Intelligence, a vast number of seemingly unrelated technological breakthroughs converge to create a front of interdependent innovations that reshape the way we live, work, and produce. Specifically for the communications sector, the EU expert body reckons that the diversity of technological domains required for future communication infrastructures highlights the relevance of multiple innovation domains [2].

In this regard, 6G radio and wireline Access technologies play a fundamental role to interconnect all different forms and grades of intelligence (human, humanoid or those in development within Datacenter facilities) in a pervasive and ubiquitous way. However, this progress puts the transport networks into a significant strain in terms of capacity and connectivity [3]. To overcome the dangers of capacity crunch and system gridlock in the network transportation segment, the unused spectrum of the single mode optical fiber (SMF) should be untapped by means of Multi-Band Wavelength Routed Networks (MB-WRNs).

In MB-WRNs, multiple spectral bands as for example C-, L-, S-, E, O- or even U- bands, span a total bandwidth of approximately 450nm [4],[5]. The exploitation of additional spectral bands not only increases the capacity of point-to-point connections but also it allows to develop

hierarchically flatter network architectures in the context of an 'optical continuum'. In this case, a larger number of direct connections between nodes is possible, limiting the number of O/E/O interfaces, and aggregation/grooming stages needed to complete an end-to-end path. In turn, this simplification lowers the total cost of ownership through the reuse of the available and deployed fiber optical infrastructure, enhances manageability and improves the end-to-end low-latency performance. In this context, only *transparent* and *translucent* paths are considered in this work, disregarding *opaque* networks as the latter only increase point-to-point capacity without offering further simplification [6].

The MB-WRNs capitalize on the framework of Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) [7] to efficiently use of the available spectrum and deploy new services cost-effectively. This way, the overall network capacity and spectral efficiency is increased since channels are packed using much narrower spectral guard bands [8].

To make the most of the MB-WRNs, it is needed to enhance network manageability, thus programmability and automation need to be introduced. Along this line, a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) control plane plays a pivotal role to dynamically manage, scale and optimize the network to meet the changing traffic demands. An SDN controller is responsible for provisioning network services and to implement complex automation tasks, such as closed-loop automation processes where certain network conditions or events trigger further actions in the network. Moreover, the decoupling of the Path Computation function out of the rest of the control plane operations provides network operators with additional flexibility when defining

network management policies to optimize routing and provisioning separately from connection management and maintenance operations. Consequently, an Optical Path Computation Element (PCE) is a dedicated entity that is tasked to compute paths given a set of constraints and the network status. Such a Path Computation function can be made accessible to clients (e.g, the optical SDN controller) using an open and standard interface. We refer to such entity as a SDN-enabled Optical PCE.

In this work, we present the design, implementation, and validation of an SDN control plane for Multi-Band optical networks with externalized path computation function. Special focus is given to present the intertwine between routing operations and physical layer impairment constraints. In Section 2, we introduce the notion of automation, and we present an overview of the MB-PCE architecture. We highlight the shortcomings of transparent networks and we elaborate the need to consider translucent paths. Section 3 presents the resource management and optimization engine, detailing the workflow of the main algorithm as well as the other auxiliary algorithms. It also details the input parameters, and it makes the case for the translucent paths. Section 4 elaborates the abstraction model for fiber propagation multi-band impairments and its validation. Section 5 and 6 are dedicated to detail the implementation and validation at the control plane level of the approach using open and standard interfaces in an environment that represents production systems, showing key aspects such as service provisioning or path computation latency.

2. AN SDN-ENABLED OPTICAL PCE FOR MB-WRNS

As it is highlighted in the introduction, network automation has a cardinal role to play in MB-WRNs to support dynamic cloud service deployment and to increase operator's turnover by reducing the time to new services.

Specifically, *automation* is key for network operators as it relates to the process by which a network is reconfigured upon network state changes with little to no (human) intervention. Macroscopically, it involves network configuration and reconfiguration (such as service provisioning) as well as performance monitoring and streaming telemetry, to implement a closed-control loop where events or patterns observed in the network trigger actions in the network. In particular, the provisioning of connectivity services is delegated to an SDN-based system that is logically centralized, as described in Section 5.

As mentioned, a particular aspect of relevance is the *decoupling of the path computation function* from the rest of the control plane operations, allowing additional flexibility to the selection of advanced routing and path allocation policies and algorithms. The PCE is then tasked to compute a path between two endpoints in the network based on an abstracted representation of this network and its connectivity including fiber propagation effects and transmission system specifications which is an inherently multi-layer operation. The PCE retains information for the status of the network and exploits suitably developed algorithms that carry out optimizations aiming to adapt network resource usage to changing conditions in an optimal manner.

The abstraction policies upon which the PCE is built hide the complexity of the underlying network technologies. For this reason, such policies should balance simplicity and computational time to respond to network events in a timely manner. As shown in sections 3 to 5 when multi-layer models are employed, the selection of the appropriate abstraction methodology is key to reduce computation times.

In this work, the path selection of a PCE readily incorporates transmission physical layer impairments of the underlying optical layer when a path is validated. For this reason, the PCE exploits a routing engine that is built upon constraint-based routing algorithms to ensure the routing decisions:

Figure 1: A schematic layout of the MB-PCE functionality

- Make the most of the available optical spectrum. For this scope routing is implemented by means of an efficient spectrum and modulation-format assignment.
- The impact of physical layer effects over the selected optical paths is readily incorporated and the results are assessed against Quality-of-Transmission (QoT) target values.
- Minimize (ideally, completely eradicate) the blocking of connections. In this way, the routing engine of the PCE ascertains the conditions that utilize the resources in the most efficient way, it maximizes the total capacity of the network while it minimizes the number of frustrated connection set-ups.

In the context of MB-WRNs these conditions are not always met in end-to-end transparent paths for several reasons. For example, this may happen when i) the attainable physical layer performance is not adequate; ii) the same number of contiguous spectral slots across a multi-hop end-to-end path are not available; c) an end-to-end path is crossing different administrative, operational and ownership network domains where different transmission and switching technologies may apply. If any of the above apply, the connection is blocked.

Physical layer limitations are the result of distinguished but intertwined transmission linear and nonlinear effects. The accumulation of Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noise, nonlinear effects that depend on the power each channel is launched and/or the total power in the fiber, transmission system configuration parameters as well as fundamental technology constraints limit the transparent length. The technology constraints include the "optoelectronic bottleneck" which was used in legacy optical transmission systems to describe the disparity between the data throughput a fiber-optic system could transmit and the speed the electronic systems could process data [9]. The "optoelectronic bottleneck" makes itself present again in EONs, this time as the discrepancy between the attainable line-rate and the symbol-rate of the digital-to-analog converter (DAC) and analog to digital converter (ADC) as it is clearly shown e.g. in Fig.3 of [10]. As a result, to attain a much higher line-rates than the native DAC/ADC rates, higher cardinality modulation formats are employed eventually limiting the attainable transparent length [10-12].

To overcome these limitations, *translucent* networks allow signal regeneration and/or spectral conversion in sparse but strategic locations in the network. The corresponding flows may not necessarily undergo a L2 aggregation, grooming and switching as sliceable, bandwidth variable transmitter and receiver [13] can be interfaced back-to-back to provide the requested functionality [14]. Nevertheless, a network with translucent paths, which may incorporate end-to-end transparent paths too, comes with the additional CapEx costs associated to these spare transceivers that need to be allocated in key network nodes.

Due to the higher sensitivity of multi-band transmission systems to physical layer degradations than C-band-only systems, a PCE for MB-WRNs should incorporate both transparent and translucent paths to enhance utilization, efficiency, and manageability.

In this work, we exploit a PCE for MB-WRNs having at its core a Physical Layer Impairment-aware Routing, Modulation and Spectrum Assignment (PLI-aware RMSA) routing engine. A schematic layout of the MB-PCE is presented in Fig.2 where the physical layer abstractions and routing and optimization algorithms are employed to maximize the utilization of the available resources and to reduce network blocking as detailed in sections 3 and 4. An open API is used to interface the MB-PCE to the Optical SDN controller detailed in section 5.

3. A MULTI-BAND OPTICAL NETWORK RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND OPTIMIZATION ENGINE

3.1. A MB-PCE: Key Elements and Concepts

A translucent end-to-end lightpath is decomposed in two or more disjoint but consecutive transparent paths where the channel is o/e regenerated at the edges of these paths. Therefore, as a translucent path is a more general category that contains transparent paths, a PLI-aware RMSA limited to networks with fully transparent paths only as in [15], finds its niche here too. In this section, this algorithm is extended to incorporate the more general case of translucent paths.

The operations of the multi-band routing engine are completed in four consecutive stages as below and the corresponding chart flow is illustrated in Fig.2.

Stage-I: Network Topology Definition and System Specifications

At this stage the details of the networks and the transmission systems under consideration are inserted as *Input* parameters to the routing engine. These are:

- *Network topology definition:* the geospatial positioning of the nodes and the connectivity pattern between them are specified; the number of edges are defined. The links interconnecting the nodes are stated together with the location of key elements like the optical amplifiers. Finally, the *k-shortest* paths for all network node pairs are defined and stored.
- *Optical system parameter definition.* These include the definition of high-level parameters, like the available optical bands, the size of the elementary Frequency Slot Unit (FSU) as of [7], the number of FSUs per band and the total capacity per band, as well as the operational parameters of the deployed transmission systems. Fig.3a illustrates the parameters that define an arbitrary point-to-point link in this work, while the tables in Fig.3b associate the per link parameters we use in our routing engine (left-hand side) to the corresponding list of parameters of the IETF standard [16] (right-hand side).
- *Traffic matrix definition:* This requires designating the demands between all nodes and their edges as well as the available line-rates and their allocation to the corresponding demands. Also,

the average time duration of the demands and the average inter-arrival time between two consecutive demands.

Figure 2: The flow chart of a multi-band PCE operation for translucent paths.

Stage-II: Formation of the Spectral and Modulation Format Assignment (SMA)

This stage is completed in two steps: In the first step, i) a preliminary spectrum and modulation format assignment (SMA) is made for several the *k-shortest* paths, and ii) the QoT metric, Optical Signal to Noise plus Interference Ratio (OSNIR) (see section 4) for these shorter paths is estimated by means of closed-form/analytic mathematical expressions.

In the second step, the two processes above are pipelined to allow the algorithm to either approve or reject the creation of a lightpath. A path is rejected if at least one of the following reasons apply:

- *Spectral slot unavailability:* no contiguous spectral slots are available in any optical band to support a transparent end-to-end connection.
- *Inadequate physical layer performance:* either the OSNIR of the candidate lightpath falls short of the QoT estimator threshold or the OSNIR of at least one of the already established lightpaths performs below the QoT threshold due to the presence of this candidate lightpath. The QoT estimator may or may not include suitably chosen *operational margins* as detailed in [15].

Figure 3: (a) The input system parameters to the multi band routing engine; (b) the parameters (on the left) in relevance to those from the IETF standard (on the right) [16].

In either case, the rejected lightpath is assigned the next available path from the sorted list of k -shortest paths and then it is re-iterated. If these paths are all rejected, the first step is repeated using, if possible, a lower cardinality SMA values. If no path is retained, the routing engine registers a blocking condition, and it designates this lightpath as a candidate for Stage-IV.

Stage-III: Finalization of Optically Transparent Paths

During this stage, the MB-PCE finalizes the transparent lightpaths [15]. The final assessment on network's throughput is completed and the lightpath is successfully pertained triggering an update of the corresponding arrays for each link across the path, e. g., the arrays of active connections, launch power, modulation format, consumed frequency slots etc.

Stage-IV: Formation of Translucent Paths

A lightpath that has been rejected during Stage-II, it is forwarded to the "Path-Split Routine" (PSR) (Fig.2) for further iteration. At this stage, the algorithm splits a rejected transparent optical path into two or more shorter-length transparent paths followed by full o/e regeneration at intermediate nodes along the original path (translucent path generation).

This way, the two (or more) shorter length transparent paths may exploit a more suitable combination of a higher cardinality modulation formats and a lower symbol-rate source. It is possible to select a different modulation format/symbol-rate pair for the newly candidate transparent paths as these are decided independently.

To understand the benefits arising from this path split, it is reminded that the number of optical slots 'consumed' by a lightpath is defined by the symbol-rate employed. To be more specific, the selected symbol-rate defines the optical bandwidth this channel consumes. Therefore, the number of FSUs a particular DAC/ADC system requires is given as the ratio of the optical bandwidth needed to the FSU spectral width (which is 12.5 GHz throughout this work). Therefore, by downgrading the symbol-rate in the candidate shorter-length transparent paths, the total number of optical slots consumed in these new paths is reduced, reducing the blocking probability due to spectral unavailability. Moreover, given the shorter transparent length of the two (or more)

paths that emerged from the original path, the chance for a better QoT performance is improved (although this cannot be guaranteed as the selection of the aforementioned parameters play a key role). Section 3.2 further provides the details of the corresponding PSR algorithms in relation to the network management policies of Fig.1.

3.2. The Path-Split Routine and the Related Algorithms

The PSR is the algorithmic procedure that splits a path P from a node S (source) to a node D (destination) into two or more consecutive paths based on constraints/criteria associated to higher-level objectives like: a quest to maximize spectral efficiency, the need to retain the network in a not blocking state, the necessity for a connection to possibly cross other administrative domains etc. It is pointed out that this is an exclusively L1 operation so no grooming or any other L2 process takes place. The *Path Split (PS)* algorithm provides as 'Output' a set of disjoint but consecutive paths out of the initial, longer, path. These solutions are the alternative candidate 'split paths' that meet the requested criteria. The corresponding algorithms are using the parameters and the variables summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables and Parameters for the Path Split Algorithms

Variable	Description
G	network topology graph
N	set of network nodes
E	set of bidirectional optical fiber links (edges)
B	set of active optical bands
C_B	set of capacities (number of frequency slot units - FSUs) for each optical band in the set B
p	Path between a source node and a destination node
p_s	source node of path p
p_n	destination node of path p
N_p	set of network nodes included in the path p , ordered from source to destination
E_p	set of edges included in the path p , ordered from source to destination
S_p	set of path-split alternatives for a specific path p as an outcome of the path split algorithms
b	optical band
R_B	set of available transmitter types for each optical band in the set B , ordered with increasing value of required FSUs for each transmitter
r	transmitter type
r_d	max distance supported by transmitter type r
r_f	number of consequent frequency slot units (FSUs) required by transmitter type r
$e_{i,j}$	Edge between node i and node j
u	Utilization of a specific edge e calculated as the ratio between all available FSUs and occupied FSUs.

INPUT: The initial path p from a source node p_s to destination node p_n . The set of network nodes N_p and the set of edges E_p included in the path p from the source to destination nodes. The band b in which the path will be allocated. The utilization threshold u_{th} is for those algorithms need to use such a parameter.

OUTPUT: A set of path-split alternatives s_p for the path p , sorted from the mostly to least preferred candidate.

The *PS* algorithm prioritizes (sorts) the candidate path splits based on a second set of criteria. These latter criteria are deduced by means of the following algorithms which are integrated into the MB-PCE's routing engine:

- High Modulation Format First Path Split (*HighMFFirst*)
- Utilization based Path Split (*UtilBasedSplit*)
- Combined Path Split with Utilization First (*CombUtilFirst*)

- Combined Path Split with Modulation Format First (*CombMFFirst*)

1. HighMFFirst: The HighMFFirst algorithm splits the initial path in two (or more) separated paths so as the highest feasible modulation formats are assigned in the newly created consecutive paths.

The main objective of this algorithm is to maximize spectral efficiency. This is done by using the highest permissible cardinality modulation format for the longest of the subsequent translucent paths and for the highest number of the incoming requests to Stage-IV. Specifically, the performed operations are detailed below:

```

Set  $S_g = \emptyset$ ;
while  $R_B$  is not empty do
  Consider the first transmitter type  $r \in R_B$ ;
  Set  $G_c = \emptyset$ ; Consider the first node  $n_i \in N_p$ ;
  while  $n_j \neq p_d$  do
    Consider the next node  $n_j \in N_p$ ;
    while  $distance(n_i, n_j) < r_d$  do
      Consider the next node  $n_j \in N_p$ ;
    end while
    Add  $n_j$  into  $G_c$ ; Set  $n_i = n_j$ ;
    Repeat the above steps starting from the last node up to the first
    node;
    Remove  $r$  from  $R_B$ ;
  end while
  if  $G_c \neq \emptyset$ 
    Add  $G_c$  into  $S_g$ ; Set  $G_c = \emptyset$ ;
  end if
end while

```

To further elaborate the operation, the functionality of the *HighMFFirst* algorithm is graphically depicted in Fig.4. In this example, we assume it is requested to route a 400Gb/s connection from node 1 to node 8 that spans a path of 1,200 km in length. If the connection is transparent, a path via nodes {1-2-3-4-6-7-8} is established as shown in Fig.4.

With the aid of Fig.3 in [10] where use is made of the case (c) with two-zone OSNIRs (zone-1: E and S₁-bands; zone-2: S₂, C and L bands) and for a transmission system employing QPSK with a 128 Gbaud symbol-rate DAC/ADC (FSU = 12.5 GHz), 11 FSUs need to be consumed in every edge across the transparent path during *Stage-II*.

However, if there no contiguous spectral slots available across the entire path during *Stage-II*, the candidate connection is forwarded to *Stage IV* where the potential for a translucent path is considered. In the translucent mode, the HighMFFirst algorithm splits the initial path {1-2-3-4-6-7-8} into the consecutive paths {1-2-3}, {3-4-6} and {6-7-8} each one allocating a different set of contiguous spectral slots (denoted with different colors) spanning a path distance of e.g., 400Km. For these newly created paths, a 32QAM modulation format and a DAC/ADC with 48 Gbaud symbol-rate is used instead, consuming 4 FSUs in every edge across the initial path, giving the chance to accommodate this connection. This algorithm is used primarily during the connection set-up phase.

Request: 400Gb/s, Path distance: 1,200Km, Source: 1 Destination: 8

Figure 4: A use-case for the HighMFFirst algorithm

2. UtilBasedSplit: The UtilBasedSplit algorithm splits the initial path based on link utilization considerations. The main objective of the algorithm is the relaxation of the frequency continuity constraint near (before or after) the network edges as slots might be unavailable only between two specific edges and not across the entire path. The *UtilBasedSplit* is used when the objective is to minimize the number of FSUs assigned in such highly utilized links. The related algorithm operations are:

```

Set  $S_g = \emptyset$ ; Set  $G_c = \emptyset$ ; Set  $N_c = \emptyset$ ;
Consider the first edge  $n_i \in N_p$ ;
while  $n_j \neq p_d$  do
  Consider the next node  $n_j \in N_p$ ;
  Consider the edge  $e_{i,j}$  between  $n_i$  and  $n_j$ ;
  if  $u_{e_{i,j}} \geq u_{th}$ 
    Add  $n_i$  into  $N_c$ ; Add  $n_j$  into  $N_c$ ; Set  $n_i = n_j$ ;
  end if
end while
while  $N_c$  is not empty do
  Consider the first node  $n \in N_c$ ;
  Add  $n$  into  $G_c$ ; Add  $G_c$  into  $S_g$ ; Set  $G_c = \emptyset$ 
end while

```

The functionality of the UtilBasedSplit algorithm is graphically depicted in Fig.5. Using the details of the previous example, we assume that the path {6,7} is highly utilized so only 5 FSUs are available. Under a transparent mode of operation, the connection is blocked due to the unavailability of FSUs along this link as the QPSK format consumes 11 FSUs.

In the translucent mode of operation under the UtilBasedSplit algorithm, the initial path {1-2-3-4-6-7-8} is split into two paths: the {1-2-4-6} of 800 km and the {6-7-8} of 400 km. Regarding the former path, a 64 Gbaud symbol-rate and a 16QAM modulation format is assigned, consuming 6 FSUs in every edge across this path. Regarding the second and most troublesome path, a 32QAM modulation format and a DAC/ADC with 48 Gbaud symbol-rate is used instead, consuming 4 FSUs. In this case, the connection can be granted under the translucent mode.

Finally, two more path-split algorithms (*CombUtilFirst* and *CombMFFirst*) are introduced that combine the functionality of the aforementioned algorithms, to maximum the gains from the available pool of transponders. These algorithms find their niche when the PCE is tasked to maintain and defragment the network during the operational phase.

Request: 400Gb/s, Path distance: 1,200Km, Source: 1 Destination: 8

Figure 5: A use-case for the UtilBasedSplit algorithm

3. CombUtilFirst: The CombUtilFirst algorithm integrates the two previous algorithms, while during the final classification, priority is given to splits offering higher FSU utilization. The main objectives of this variant are: a) if a network is underutilized, it would maximize spectral efficiency; b) if a network is congested it would both relax the frequency continuity constrain and it will maximize spectral efficiency. The related algorithm operations are:

```

Set  $S_g = \emptyset$ ; Apply HighMFFirst algorithm;
Consider  $S_{g,metf}$  the outcome of METF-PS algorithm;
Add  $S_{g,metf}$  into  $S_g$ ; Apply UBF-PS algorithm;
Consider  $S_{g,ubf}$  the outcome of UBF-PS algorithm;
while  $S_{g,ubf}$  is not empty do
  Consider the first path split alternative  $G_c \in S_{g,ubf}$ ;
  if  $G_c \cap S_g = \emptyset$ 
    Add  $G_c$  into  $S_g$ ;
  end if
  Remove  $G_c$  from  $S_{g,ubf}$ ;
end while

```

4. CombMFFirst: The CombMFFirst integrates the first two algorithms, but in this case, priority is given to path splits that allow the higher modulation format cardinality while simultaneously lowering the demand from the corresponding symbol-rate. The main objective of the algorithm is, like of the *CombUtilFirst*, to maximize the spectral efficiency while relaxing the frequency continuity constraints.

4. THE ABSTRACTION MODEL FOR THE OPTICAL FIBER PROPAGATION IMPAIRMENTS

As detailed in sections 2 and 3, an abstract model of the multi-band physical layer impairments due to the propagation along a fiber-optic link is readily integrated into MB-PCE's routing engine. The abstraction methodology is the same as in [15] while the quantity OSNIR is the metric used to weight the QoT. The OSNIR accounts for ASE noise accumulation and for fiber nonlinearities. The latter incorporate both intra-band effects, like cross-channel interference (XCI- eq.4 in [15]), and self-channel interference (SCI- eq.3 in [15]), as well as inter-band effects, like Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS). The SRS, although it is not a dominant degradation effect in C-band only transmission system, it may lead to a severe performance degradation in MB-WRNs. In fact, the power transfer from lower to higher wavelength channels due to SRS results to a considerable power depletion for the former. Accordingly, the OSNIR is given by eq. (1).

$$OSNIR = \frac{P_{ch,i} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{N_s} G_{SRS,j}}{P_{ASE,i} + P_{NLI-intra,i}} \quad (1)$$

where $P_{ch,i}$ is the power of the i^{th} channel at node ingress/egress, $P_{ASE,i}$ and $P_{NLI-intra,i}$ denote the powers due to ASE accumulation and the intra-band nonlinearities for the i^{th} channel at the end of the path, respectively, while the $G_{SRS,j}$ accounts for the SRS Gain/Loss effect in the j^{th} fiber span.

In eq. (1) the intra-band and inter-band effects are considered as two independent phenomena with no cross-coupling between them i.e., the transmission system operates in the 'weak nonlinearity' regime where the power transfer due to SRS does not significantly affect the evolution of XCI/SCI. As it has been shown in [17-19] and in Fig. 4b of [21], as long as the total power in the optical fiber does not significantly exceed the +21 dBm, the assumption of no cross-coupling between nonlinearities holds. In section 4.2 it will be made clear that the 'weak nonlinearity' conditions do apply when the operational parameters of the transmission system are dully optimized.

In [20], the SRS is estimated for a maximum channel spacing of up to 15 THz in-line with the so-called 'triangular approximation'. However, the true Raman curve is extended in frequency up to approximately 35 THz (see Fig.6). In this work, the impact of this extended spectrum is taken into consideration following the formalism of [22] where the true Raman spectrum beyond a 15 THz channel spacing is approximated as a logarithmic tail.

Figure 6: True and approximated Raman spectrum for a standard single mode fiber.

Because the MB-PCE is carrying out consecutive operations of considerable computational complexity, it is imperative the abstraction models that account for the physical layer phenomena to returned results in a timely fashion. To ensure this is the case, the corresponding physical effects are abstracted by means of the aforementioned closed-form mathematical expressions. It is possible that semi-analytical approaches, such as [23] to be considered as well. In the employed abstraction model, several approximations are necessary to derive these closed-form expressions. The list of assumptions used to abstract the transmission effects are summarized in section 4 of [15] and they all apply here, too. We opted for the closed-form formalism of [15] to estimate the impact of physical layer effects for MB transmission over other closed-form alternatives of the "Gaussian-Noise" family like [23]-[25] as a) it can quantify the impact of SRS for systems extending beyond 15 THz, allowing to estimate the inter-band effects for three or more amplification bands, b) it is shown to be very accurate in links with span length smaller than 30 km, which is critical for core networks, like the one considered here, as it includes links down to 2 km.

4.1. Validation of the Spectrally Extended SRS Model

To further validate the accuracy of the SRS model of [22], a 100G-line-rate/32 Gbaud/QPSK multi-band transmission system is considered and the gain or depletion of a channel's power due to SRS, G_{SRS} , is

estimated at the end of *single* fiber span of 50 km in length, i.e. at the output of the band multiplexer of Fig.2a, as a function of the launch power at fiber input. We consider two transmission systems/scenarios with 305 and 505 channels in total, operating at the Nyquist rate with 61 and 101 consecutive channels per band, respectively, for the E, S, C and L-bands. The G_{SRS} is calculated for the central channel in each band. We have excluded O and U-bands from this study, as they would limit the number of simulated channels (in VPI), due to the need to extend the simulation bandwidth.

Other physical layer parameters for these multi band systems are given in Table 2. These include, the central wavelength (λ) of each band and the values for the fiber attenuation (α), dispersion (D), nonlinear coefficient (γ), effective area (A_{eff}) per band and noise figure (NF) of the different amplifiers (see Fig.3a), as these fiber parameters are wavelength dependent. To compensate for the losses, xDFA amplifiers are used as in [10]: a Bismuth-DFA for the E-band while the S band is segregated in two sub-bands (S_1 -band and S_2 -band) to ensure the corresponding amplifiers provide sufficient power per channel [15] so two separate Thulium-DFAs are used for the S_1 and S_2 -bands. Finally, two Erbium-DFAs are optimized for the C and L bands. The values of the corresponding NFs are as in [10].

Table 2: The Parameters of the Multi Band Transmission Systems

	E band	S ₁ band	S ₂ band	C band	L band
λ (nm) - central	1416.5	1466.7	1496.7	1546.9	1594.6
α (dB/km)	0.280	0.246	0.229	0.211	0.210
D (ps/nm/km)	8.63	12.06	13.97	16.96	19.60
γ (1/W/km)	1.65	1.50	1.44	1.32	1.24
A_{eff} (μm^2)	70	74	76	80	83
NF (dB)	6	5.5	5.5	5.5	6

Furthermore, the results from the closed-form abstraction model are assessed against those from a commercially available simulation tool (VPI) which employ the Split Step Fourier Method (SSF) to numerically solve the corresponding nonlinear propagation equations in an optical fiber by making use of the true Raman spectrum.

Figure 7: The spectrum with 305 channels across the E, S, C and L-bands

The following parameters are used for the numerical simulation tool: 8,192 bits per polarization; the “universal” fiber type is utilized to ensure that the power exchange due to SRS between any pair of channels across the entire spectrum, from the E to the L band, is accounted for; the “sample-mode bandwidth” is set for 32.7 THz. At the end of each fiber segment, a “WDM_DEMUX” is placed, with “rectangular” shaped filters, to split the spectrum in bands and to amplify each band separately, followed by a “WDM_MUX” in tandem as in Fig.3a. A further

2 dB insertion loss is added to the loss budget of each span to compensate for the band mux/demux. To mitigate the impact of chromatic dispersion and polarization mode dispersion, the in-built to the simulation tool digital signal processing (DSP) module at the receiver is used. To estimate the SRS Gain, we measured the optical power of each channel at fiber input and compared it with its power after the corresponding per band doped fiber amplifier that compensated exactly the fiber loss. Finally, eq.(5) of [26] is used to extract the corresponding OSNR value from the respective BER values VPI returns. To estimate the OSNR using VPI we set the corresponding wavelength dependent physical layer parameters, e.g. a , D , A_{eff} , using text files. Indicatively, for a system with 305 channels over the E, S, C and L-bands, the spectrum is as shown in Fig.7.

To benchmark the two abstraction methods, the closed-form approach and the numerical one, for a fiber span of 50 km in length and for two configurations with 305 (61 channels per band) and 505 channels (101 channels per band), respectively, the launch power is iterated from -8 dBm per channel to -1 dBm and from -8 dBm per channel to -3 dBm per channel, respectively. These power per channel values correspond to a total optical power in the fiber of the order of ~250 mW. It is important to point out that all channels are simultaneously set to the same power level as the power is iterated at system’s ingress. The estimated G_{SRS} gain is shown in Fig.8a, b for the case of 65 and 101 channels per band, respectively.

Figure 8: Benchmarking of the closed-form model against the corresponding numerical results with SSF for G_{SRS} vs power per channel considering a 50 km link with (a) 305 channels; (b) 505 channels.

In both cases, the maximum deviation between the analytical and numerical methods is of the order of 1 dB for up to +23 dBm total power in the fiber. These findings are in-line with the restrictions elaborated in

the previous section for the total power within any fiber segment that keep the system in the weak-nonlinearity regime. Evidently, from Fig. 8 the impact of the SRS for a single fiber span becomes increasingly critical as the number of channels in the system and/or the power per channel increases. As a result, considerable power is transferred from E- and S-bands to L- and C-bands.

4.2. Optimal Conditions for the Physical Layer Abstraction Model in the Context of the MB-PCE

As it is pointed out in [10],[15],[22], the approach adopted in section 4.1 where all channels are loaded at the same power level, although it is a reasonable assumption when the quest is to pinpoint the physical phenomenon in isolation, it is a sub-optimal approach when it comes to deduce the operational conditions as part of the MB-PCE operations. As the scope of this work is the latter, additional algorithmic and design steps are introduced:

4.2.1 Power Launch Optimization Strategy: Following [10],[15] and based on high-level decisions for the utility and the management of the different optical bands (network management policies Fig.1), the OSNIR for the channels within each band are co-optimized against the requested transparent length and band functionality. Indicatively, in [10] the two out of the three exploitation schemes considered there, are as follows: in the first one, the OSNIR is requested to have a 'flat' (less than 1-dB) variation across the entire E-band to L-band spectrum. This is achieved by means of suitably chosen launch powers per band, under the constraints for the maximum total power etc. as in [10],[15]. In the second scheme, the OSNIR performance in the C and L-bands is maximized at the expense of the performance for the S and E-bands, using Pch/band as an optimization parameter. This scheme leads to a 'step-like' OSNIR performance where the C, L and S₂ bands aim to serve long-haul connections while E and S₁ bands are used for shorter-length connections only. In both cases, the corresponding Pch/band values are returned from the optimization algorithm that ensures the requested OSNIR performance.

The optimization is formulated using the well-known Simulated annealing algorithm [27] and the operations are as below:

```

Initialize Pch per band values;
Set E = current system energy;
Set T = start temperature;
while T > end temperature do
  Modify one band's Pch value;
  Set E' = current system energy;
  Set ΔE = E' - E;
  if ΔE < 0 or e-ΔE / (K * T) > some uniform random number
    Set E = E';
  else
    Undo earlier Pch modification;
  end if
  Multiply T by the cooling rate;
end while

```

The system energy is given by eq. (2)

$$E = \sum_{band} \frac{C_{band}}{OSNIR_{band}^2} \quad (2)$$

where the constants C_{band} allows the aforementioned relative tuning of the OSNIR performance per band and the $OSNIR_{band}$ values are calculated using eq. (1). Given that the model of eq. (1) internally works with a discrimination of the power levels down to the individual channel, this approach can be further expanded towards a more fine-grained power optimization, partitioning each band in smaller segments, but this variation is not explored further here.

4.2.2. Compensation for the SRS Effect and Validation: Despite the introduction of the optimization method of 4.2.1, the effect of SRS should be countered at regular intervals. Authors suggested to compensate SRS per fiber span [28] while in [10],[15],[22] the compensation of SRS takes place at a node based on Wavelength Selective Switch (WSS) elements.

Here we assume a path layout as in Fig.9 with an optical node every third fiber span of 50 kms (inter-node distance, 150 km) to compensate for the SRS. We assess the OSNIR performance of a link with 155 channels across the E to L-band spectrum and a total length of 1,200 km. The line-rate is 100G/32 Gbaud, the modulation format is QPSK and the launch powers per band as of Table 3. The optical bandwidth for this particular study for the estimation of ASE noise is set to 32 GHz (equal to the baud rate).

Figure 9: A schematic representation of the abstraction model that emulates the corresponding transmission system. SRS is compensated at the Optical, WSS-based, Node.

The results from the closed-form expressions in our routing engine are benchmarked against those from the numerical simulation tool and they are illustrated in Fig.10.

Table 3: Launch powers per band for a 'flat' OSNIR

E-band (dBm)	S ₁ -band (dBm)	S ₂ -band (dBm)	C-band (dBm)	L-band (dBm)
-1.97	-6.84	-8.2	-9	-8.14

It is evident from Fig.10 that the proposed abstraction method that uses closed-form expressions allows to predict the transmission performance of an optical multi-band transmission system with sufficient accuracy.

Figure 10: The OSNIR performance for a link of 1,200 km with 155 channels allocated from the E-band to the L-band (100G per λ/QPSK).

Moreover, with a suitable optimization of the launch power, different band-management objectives are feasible. Also, it is pointed out the vast difference in the computational time between the two methods: the execution time for the abstraction method based on closed-form expressions is less than second while the script from the numerical tool was running for over two days. This confirms that in the context of MB-PCE operations, only the former method may return results in a timely manner. Finally, it should be reported that we have not been able to

of frequency slots and the selected transmission system parameters (note that in this work we have considered single OTSi). The SDN controller instantiates the DSR, OTSi and MC layers connection and connection end point (CEPs) objects, it configures the transceivers' operational modes and the media channels in the ROADM devices via the SBI interface.

Figure 13: SDN workflow for the provisioning of a DSR connectivity service. Note the intermediate request of the TAPI context (including topology): this corresponds to the *on-demand polling* to synchronize state between the Optical SDN controller and the MB-PCE.

6. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE SDN-BASED AUTOMATION

This section details the experimental evaluation of the SDN-enabled MB-PCE, supported over a distributed control plane testbed that consist of the CTTC optical SDN controller (with IP, e.g., 10.8.0.2) and the OLC-E's MB-PCE (with IP, e.g., 10.8.0.6) which are connected via tunnels over

the public Internet. The emulated network is BT's optical mesh shown in Fig.14 that consists of 22 ROADM nodes, 56 amplifiers, 28 terminal devices (106 network elements in total) and 238 unidirectional links. For the scope of this experiment, it is assumed that each link may support E, S, C and L bands.

Figure 14: BT's optical mesh with 22 ROADM nodes, 56 amplifiers, 28 terminal devices (106 network elements in total) and 238 unidirectional links

We have developed hypothetical scenarios where multiple connection requests need to be provisioned between the *node_ROADM1* and the *node_ROADM 2* in Fig.15. To do so, the optical SDN controller delegates the path computation task to the MB-PCE which, upon request, retrieves (if needed) the network topology and the list of active services/connections from the optical SDN controller. Subsequently, the MB-PCE executes the PLI-aware RMSA algorithm and for each of these

Figure 15: The different scenarios are considered requesting services between ROADM-1 and ROADM-2 using multiple transceivers.

requests it returns to the optical SDN controller the selected path as well as the configuration details and their operational parameters for each network element along this link.

In the following three scenarios, the routing engine of the MB-PCE is instructed to check the potential of the available bands to support service connection requests. For such scenarios, the MB-PCE is instructed to iterate available bands with the same order of preference as {C, E, L, S₁, S₂} so if the C-band is not available, the routing engine proceeds to the second best which is the E-band and so on. We wish to investigate the effectiveness of the MB-PCE and its behavior/response against legitimate and illegitimate instructions from the OMB SDN controller. The latter could be misconfigurations or even deliberate/malicious acts.

6.1. Scenario A

In this first hypothetical case, we wish to investigate the impact of a deliberate or accidental physical layer misconfiguration instruction on the completion (or not) of service requests in the case of fully transparent paths.

The 400G DSR service between two transceivers at the source-destination nodes, *node_101* and *node_102* in Fig.15, is indicated by means of the corresponding Service Interface Points (SIPs) and Fig.16 shows the provisioning of a connection request using the TAPI connectivity model. The 400G line-rate is based on a 16QAM, 48 Gbaud symbol-rate transceivers. We proceed to a deliberate misconfiguration of PHY parameters, so the optimal launch power algorithm of section 4.2.1 is turned off. Then, the optical SDN controller sends service requests, and it instructs the MB-PCE to launch the power of the C-band channels at +1 dBm per channel while the channels in E-band are set to optimal launch power. The selected powers render the C-band unusable as the RMSA algorithm returns no route for the connection requests. As a result, the algorithm proceeds to assess the potential of the E-band to support the connection service (second band in the list) and it, indeed, grants these requests to the E-band. It is critically important for network operators that no misconfigured paths for the connection requests are selected.

Time	Source	Destination	Length	Info
0.000724820	SDN-CTRL_NBI	CLIENT	424	HTTP/1.1 200 OK
REF	CLIENT	SDN-CTRL_NBI	1051	POST /restconf/data/tapi-common:cont
2.845515112	SDN-CTRL_NBI	CLIENT	393	HTTP/1.1 201 Created
5.050251081	CLIENT	SDN-CTRL_NBI	544	GET /restconf/data/tapi-common:cont


```

> Hypertext Transfer Protocol
  > JavaScript Object Notation: application/json
    > Object
      > Member Key: tapi-connectivity:connectivity-service
        > Array
          > Object
            > Member Key: uuid
            > Member Key: direction
              String value: UNIDIRECTIONAL
              Key: direction
            > Member Key: layer-protocol-name
              String value: DSR
              Key: layer-protocol-name
            > Member Key: layer-protocol-qualifier
            > Member Key: end-point
              > Array
                > Object
                  > Member Key: layer-protocol-name
                  > Member Key: layer-protocol-qualifier
                  > Member Key: service-interface-point
                  > Member Key: direction:
                  > Member Key: local-id
                > Object
                  > Member Key: layer-protocol-name
                  > Member Key: layer-protocol-qualifier
                  > Member Key: service-interface-point
                  > Member Key: direction:
                  > Member Key: local-id
              Key: end-point
            > Member Key: route-objective-function
            > Member Key: connectivity-constraint
              > Object
                > Member Key: connectivity-direction
                  String value: UNIDIRECTIONAL
                  Key: connectivity-direction
                > Member Key: requested-capacity
                  > Object
                    > Member Key: total-size
                    > Object
                      > Member Key: value
  
```

Figure 16. Wireshark capture of the RESTCONF HTTP/POST operation for the creation of the connectivity service.

6.2. Scenario B

In the second scenario, the deliberate misconfiguration of the PHY parameters is less dramatic. The procedure of *Scenario A* is repeated and the optical SDN controller sends sequentially 3 service requests but now, the MB-PCE is instructed to launch the power of the C-band channels at +0.6 dBm per channel (the E-band uses the optimal launch power). As it is shown in Fig. 17, the first two requests are granted in the C-band albeit the PLI-aware RMSA algorithm selects a larger guard-band between the channels serving these two successive requests. In particular, the two requests are allocated to channels spectrally space by 162.5 GHz (or 13 FSUs) which corresponds to over three times the channel's optical bandwidth. At such wide guard-band, the effect of XCI is minimized.

However, the third request is not allocated to the C-band as the overall efficiency in FSU utilization is low in this band under these conditions. Therefore, the third connection request is allocated to the E-band as it is illustrated in Fig. 17. It is pointed out that the distances between *node_101* and *node_102* in Fig.15 are short raising no concerns for the attainable transparent length in either band.

The important conclusion is that the PLI-aware RMSA can identify operational parameters even under adverse conditions and is able to 'switch' between bands in the case of blocking.

Figure 17: Graphical representation of the spectrum usage of the link between ROADM1 and ROADM2 showing the gap between services in the C-band and a third service in the E-band.

6.3. Scenario C

In this third scenario, the same processes are repeated but this time the optical SDN controllers sends to the MB-PCE, five service requests sequentially designating a -3.7 dBm launch power for all of them which is with acceptable range of powers (albeit non-optimal). Given the light traffic load, the PLI-aware RMSA does not observe any OSNIR degradation, so all service requests are granted spectrally successive channels in the C-band. This is clearly illustrated in Fig. 18.

Also, of interest is to measure the response time (latency) needed to complete the provisioning processes in the three scenarios. Fig.19 shows the exchange of messages between the optical SDN controller and the MB-PCE. These messages include the messages sent by the optical SDN controller to the MB-PCE related to the TAPI operations to synchronize and update the MB-PCE on the current network status. It is pointed out that as part of further optimization of the control-plane operations, only the initial synchronization is mandatory; beyond that, only the synchronization for the status of the active services is

necessary.

Figure 18. Graphical representation of the spectrum usage of the link between ROADM 1 and 2, showing 5 services using the C band

This is understood as follows: as a service provisioning operation may fail during the path computation phase, there might be a misconception between the optical SDN controller and the MB-PCE for the actual state of the network, a so regular message exchange between the two entities is necessary.

Figure 19. Wireshark capture of the Path Computation exchange, showing a path computation latency of approximately 2.5 seconds, including the dynamic retrieval of the TAPI context from the controller.

The MB-PCE latency for scenario C was measured to be in the range between 1.8 – 2.2 seconds. This value depends on whether the MB-PCE is also tasked to retrieve the network topology as explained above (first request in the series). On the contrary, this latency is two orders of magnitude lower, ranging between 17ms and 36 ms, when the network status was already up to date (assuming state synchronization). In contrast, for scenarios A and B, the deliberate degradation of the OSNIR rendered a large number of the listed frequency slots as ‘unavailable/void’, so the RMSA algorithm had to execute the PHY layer validation process thousands of times resulting to considerable delays for the MB-PCE to return results. For these two scenarios A and B, the latency is measured to be between 2.5 and 3.2 seconds.

These results confirm the assumption of section 3 and 4, i.e., the importance to incorporate to the routing engine a PLI-aware RMSA based on closed-form expression as this is the only way to attain service provisioning within a time frame compatible to the dynamicity of the events that take place in the F6G transportation network. This is particularly true as the projected capacity for the F6G transportation network would entail several hundred connection requests. Moreover, to ensure the scalability of the MB-PCE and the optical SDN controller, it is crucial to use rapidly converging algorithms to determine the optimization launch power per band or even per channel. Finally, the resiliency of the MB-PCE against misconfigurations is proved.

6. CONCLUSION

The deployment of an SDN control plane is of clear interest for network operators, notably in highly dynamic scenarios and as a key enabler for network automation. Recently, the complexity of path computation in optical networks (and, in particular, in multi-band optical transport networks with non-negligible physical layer impairments) has motivated the introduction of split architectures with the decoupling of the path computation function. In this work, we have introduced the design of such MB-PCE, validating the set of abstractions that have been made, and showing its applicability in a few scenarios with selected backbone networks. Regarding service provisioning, the latency introduced is within accepted ranges, where hardware configuration latencies are typically larger.

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References

1. A. Stavdas, "Networked Intelligence: A Wider Fusion of Technologies that Spurs the Fourth Industrial Revolution", World Review of Political Economy, Part I: Foundations, Vo.12 (2), p.220-235, 2021; Part II: The Transformation of Production Systems, Vo.12 (2), p.236-254, 2021
2. NetworkEurope; "Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2022 networks". Online: <https://www.networkeurope.eu/sria-2022-announcement/>
3. ITU-T G.Sup66 -201907, "5G wireless fronthaul requirements in passive optical network context", 07/2019

4. A. Stavdas; "Architectural solutions towards a 1,000 channel ultra-wideband WDM network". SPIE Optical Networks Magazine, Vol.2 No.1, pp. 51-60, 2001
5. T. Hoshida, V. Curri, L. Galdino, D. T. Neilson, W. Forsysiak, J. K. Fischer, T. Kato, and P. Poggiolini, "Ultrawideband systems and networks: Beyond C and L-band," *Proc. IEEE* 110, 1725–1741 (2022)
6. B. Ramamurthy, H. Feng, D. Datta, J. P. Heritage and B. Mukherjee; "Transparent vs. opaque vs. translucent wavelength-routed optical networks," *Optical Fiber Communication Conference*, 1999, San Diego, CA, USA, 1999, pp. 59-61 vol.1
7. Spectral Grids for WDM Applications: DWDM Frequency Grid, document ITU-T G.694.1, Oct. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-G.694.1/en>
8. A. Lord, S. J. Savory, M. Tornatore and A. Mitra, "Flexible Technologies to Increase Optical Network Capacity," in *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 110 (11), pp. 1714-1724, November 2022
9. A. Stavdas (Editor); "Core and Metro Networks", John-Wiley (March 2010), ISBN: 978-0-470-51274-6.
10. D. Uzunidis, C. Matrakidis, E. Kosmatos, A. Stavdas, P. Petropoulos, A. Lord, "Connectivity Challenges in E, S, C and L Optical Multi-Band Systems"; *European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2021, Bordeaux, 2021*
11. P. Poggiolini et al., "Analytical and Experimental Results on System Maximum Reach Increase Through Symbol Rate Optimization," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 1872-1885, 15 April 2016, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2016.2516398.
12. T. Gerard et al., "Relative impact of channel symbol rate on transmission capacity," in *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. B1-B8, April 2020, doi: 10.1364/JOCN.12.0000B1.
13. Laia Nadal, Michela Svaluto Moreolo, Josep M. Fàbrega, and F. Javier Vilchez, "SDN-Enabled Multi-Band S-BVT Within Disaggregated Optical Networks," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 40, 3479-3485 (2022)
14. E. Kosmatos, T. Orphanoudakis, C. Matrakidis, A. Stavdas and A. Lord; "Switchless Elastic Rate Node (SERANO) Architecture: A Universal Node for Optical Grooming and Adaptive Networking", *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications & Networking*, Vol. 8(7), A162-A170, 2016
15. D. Uzunidis, E. Kosmatos, C. Matrakidis, A. Stavdas and A. Lord, "Strategies for Upgrading an Operator's Backbone Network Beyond the C-Band: Towards Multi-Band Optical Networks," in *IEEE Photonics Journal*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1-18, April 2021.
16. IETF, "A YANG Data Model for Optical Impairment-aware Topology", version 12. Available at: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-ccamp-optical-impairment-topology-yang/12/> (March, 13, 2023).
17. L. Galdino et al., "Optical Fibre Capacity Optimisation via Continuous Bandwidth Amplification and Geometric Shaping," in *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 32, no. 17, pp. 1021-1024, 1 Sept. 2020.
18. B. J. Puttnam, R. S. Luís, G. Rademacher, Y. Awaji and H. Furukawa, "319 Tb/s Transmission over 3001 km with S, C and L band signals over >120nm bandwidth in 125 µm wide 4-core fiber," *2021 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2021, pp. 1-3.
19. B. J. Puttnam, R. S. Luís, G. Rademacher, M. Mendez-Astudilio, Y. Awaji and H. Furukawa, "S, C and Extended L-Band Transmission with Doped Fiber and Distributed Raman Amplification," *2021 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2021, pp. 1-3.
20. R. Casellas et al; "An SDN Control Plane for Multiband Networks Exploiting a PLI-aware Routing Engine". In *Optical Fiber Communication Conference 2022, W1F-2, 2022*
21. Daniel Semrau, Robert I. Killey, and Polina Bayvel, "The Gaussian Noise Model in the Presence of Inter-Channel Stimulated Raman Scattering," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 36, 3046-3055 (2018).
22. D. Uzunidis, K. Nikolaou, C. Matrakidis, A. Stavdas, A. Lord; "Closed-form Expressions for the Impact of Stimulated Raman Scattering Beyond 15 THz", *European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2022, Basel, 2022.*
23. A. D'Amico et al, "Scalable and Disaggregated GGN Approximation Applied to a C+L+S Optical Network," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 3499–3511, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2022.3162134.
24. D. Semrau, E. Sillekens, R. I. Killey and P. Bayvel, "A Modulation Format Correction Formula for the Gaussian Noise Model in the Presence of Inter-Channel Stimulated Raman Scattering," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 37, no. 19, pp. 5122-5131, 1 Oct. 2019.
25. C. Lasagni, P. Serena and A. Bononi, "Modeling Nonlinear Interference With Sparse Raman-Tilt Equalization," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 39, no. 15, pp. 4980-4989, Aug. 1, 2021.
26. Alessio Ferrari, Mark Filer, Karthikeyan Balasubramanian, Yawei Yin, Esther Le Rouzic, Jan Kundrát, Gert Grammel, Gabriele Galimberti, and Vittorio Curri, "GNPy: an open source application for physical layer aware open optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 12, C31-C40 (2020)
27. D. Uzunidis, C. Matrakidis, and A. Stavdas, "Application of a simplified FWM expression in mixed-fiber links," in *2016 24th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR)*, 2016.
28. S. Kirkpatrick, C.D. Gelatt Jr and M.P. Vecchi, "Optimization by simulated annealing". *Science*, vol. 220, no. 4598, pp. 671-680, May 13, 1983.
29. A. Ferrari et al., "Assessment on the Achievable Throughput of Multi-Band ITU-T G.652.D Fiber Transmission Systems," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 38, no. 16, pp. 4279-4291, 15 Aug. 15, 2020, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2020.2989620.
30. Huaijian Luo, Jianing Lu, Zhuili Huang, Changyuan Yu, and Chao Lu, "Optimization strategy of power control for C+L+S band transmission using a simulated annealing algorithm," *Opt. Express* 30, 664–675 (2022).
31. F. Hamaoka, M. Nakamura, S. Okamoto, K. Minoguchi, T. Sasai, A. Matsushita, E. Yamazaki, and Y. Kisaka, "Ultra-wideband WDM transmission in S-, C-, and L-bands using signal power optimization scheme," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 37(8), 1764–1771 (2019).
32. B. Correia, R. Sadeghi, E. Virgillito, A. Napoli, N. Costa, J. Pedro, and V. Curri, "Power control strategies and network performance assessment for C+ L+ S multiband optical transport," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 13(7), 147–157 (2021).
33. R. Casellas et al., "Advances in SDN control and telemetry for beyond 100G disaggregated optical networks [Invited]," in *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. C23-C37, June 2022, doi: 10.1364/JOCN.451516.
34. K. Ishii et al., "Two-Level Abstraction Approach for SDN-based Service Provisioning in Open Line Systems Featuring TAPI Externalized Path Computation," *2020 European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC)*, Brussels, Belgium, 2020, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/ECOC48923.2020.9333136.
35. R. Casellas, A. Mazzini, N. Davis, editors, ONF TR-547 v1.1, "TAPI Reference Implementation Agreement", December 2021, online https://opennetworking.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/TR-547-TAPI_ReferenceImplementationAgreement_v1.1.pdf